

A Box-Model Approach to Quantify Ocean Model Spin-Up Errors and Constrain Long-Term Trend Estimates

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ABSTRACT

Ocean regional climate models require a spin-up phase to reach thermodynamic equilibrium before being used for climate projections. When spin-up is insufficient, models retain memory of their initial conditions, introducing systematic drifts that can contaminate long-term temperature and salinity trend estimates. This paper presents a box-model framework designed to emulate the large-scale heat and salt content variability of the Mediterranean Sea and to quantify errors in long-term trend estimates arising from inadequate spin-up. The box model is calibrated using the CNRM-RCSM6 regional climate model control run, and subsequently forced with multi-centennial output from the CNRM-ESM2 global model to characterize natural variability and its influence on trend uncertainty. We show that the box model successfully reproduces the behaviour of the reference simulation for surface and intermediate layers, providing an efficient tool for sensitivity experiments. By comparing modelled and observed trends against a natural variability uncertainty envelope, we derive acceptance criteria for spin-up adequacy across different Mediterranean sub-basins and depth layers. The approach enables the quantification of spurious trends induced by initial imbalances and offers a computationally inexpensive method to estimate stable initial conditions, potentially accelerating the spin-up procedure for future model integrations.

Keywords: *ocean model spin-up; Mediterranean Sea; box model; long-term trends; natural variability; regional climate modelling; CORDEX*

1. INTRODUCTION

The spin-up problem is a fundamental challenge in ocean regional climate modelling. Before a model can be used to simulate the present-day climate or produce future projections, it must be integrated long enough for its thermodynamic state to reach equilibrium with its forcing. When this equilibration is incomplete, the model retains a memory of its (often arbitrary) initial

conditions, leading to a systematic drift that contaminates both the mean state and the temporal trends of simulated variables such as temperature and salinity.

This issue is particularly relevant in the Mediterranean Sea, a semi-enclosed basin with a complex thermohaline circulation and strong sensitivity to surface fluxes and water exchanges through the Strait of Gibraltar. Ensemble simulations have demonstrated large inter-model differences in long-term temperature and salinity evolution, as well as notable discrepancies with observational products (Harzallah et al., 2016). These differences can arise from model-specific characteristics as well as from different spin-up strategies and initial conditions.

A key practical question for regional climate modelling protocols is whether it is worth running models for long spin-up periods, and what the quantitative consequences are of starting from imbalanced conditions. Two main spin-up strategies exist: running the model for extended periods to reach stability (which can be computationally very expensive) or accepting a short spin-up with an explicit drift (which would question the suitability of the model to characterize forced long-term trends).

Constraining models with observations is a natural approach to assessing spin-up quality, but this is complicated by several factors. First, different observational products (e.g., MEDHYMAP v2.2, MEDAR, ORAS4, EN4) show important similarities but also non-negligible differences, particularly in deep layers (Figure 1). Second, the length of the observational record influences trend estimates significantly: trends computed over 20, 40, or 60 years can differ substantially due to natural variability superimposed on the forced signal (Figure 2). Third, observational products may contain a climate change signal that models are not designed to reproduce, or they may be incompatible with certain model configurations.

To address these challenges, we develop a lightweight box-model framework that captures the essential large-scale dynamics of Mediterranean heat and salt content variability. Rather than relying on computationally expensive sensitivity experiments with full numerical models, the box model can be calibrated to emulate a specific numerical model and then used to generate long synthetic runs that quantify the natural variability envelope of trend estimates. This envelope then serves as a reference against which modelled and observed trends can be compared, providing a principled and computationally efficient criterion for spin-up adequacy.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section 2 describes the observational context and the problem of trend uncertainty. Section 3 presents the box model framework and its calibration against the CNRM-RCSM6 model. Section 4 describes the multi-centennial experiments and the resulting characterization of natural variability. Section 5 addresses the impact of initial imbalances on projected values. Section 6 presents the acceptance criteria for spin-up adequacy and summary tables. Section 7 discusses the results and outlines next steps.

Figure 1: Basin averaged temperature over the Mediterranean Sea (°C) from an ensemble of Med-CORDEX simulations. Series from the two observational products (RIXEN and EN4) are also shown with their associated uncertainty (shaded areas). Adapted from Harzallah et al. (2016)

2. OBSERVATIONAL CONTEXT AND THE PROBLEM OF TREND UNCERTAINTY

2.1 Mediterranean Temperature and Salinity Trends

Observational products for the Mediterranean Sea document a general warming and salinification trend over the last several decades, consistent with anthropogenic forcing and changes in the regional hydrological cycle. However, the magnitude and vertical distribution of these trends depend strongly on which product is used and over what period the trend is estimated.

To deepen on that extent, we analyze temperature and salinity data from four observational products: MEDHYMAP v2.2, MEDAR, ORAS4, and EN4. The products are compared across four depth layers — 0–150 m (surface), 150–600 m (intermediate), 600 m–bottom (deep), and the full water column — separately for the Western and Eastern Mediterranean sub-basins. While the products agree on the overall sign of the trends in most layers, they show notable quantitative differences, particularly in the intermediate and deep layers where observational coverage is sparse.

Figure 2: Basin averaged temperature (top row, °C) and salinity (bottom row, psu) for different layers (0-150m, left), (150-600m, middle) and (600m-bottom, right). Several observational products are used: Rixen et al. (blue patch), MEDHYMAP (red line), ORAS4 reanalysis (blue line) and EN4 (green line). Figure courtesy of F. Sevault (CNRM).

2.2 Dependence of Trend Estimates on Record Length

Using the MEDHYMAP v2.2 product as a reference, we investigate how trend estimates depend on the length of the observational record. Specifically, we compute linear trends of temperature and salinity for sub-periods of 20, 40, and 60 years extracted from the full MEDHYMAP time series (Figure 3). The results reveal a strong dependence on record length: shorter records yield highly variable trend estimates, with ranges that can be two to three times larger than the trend computed over the full record.

This finding has direct implications for model evaluation. If a model is evaluated against observed trends computed over a short period, the uncertainty in the observed estimate itself could be so large that it provides only weak constraints on the model. The same conclusion applies for salinity, with somewhat different uncertainty ranges by layer.

The above analysis leads to the following key insight: observed trends cannot be used directly as hard constraints on model simulations without accounting for the uncertainty due to natural variability. Even if a model is perfectly forced and free of spin-up artifacts, its simulated trend over any finite period will deviate from the true forced trend due to internal variability. A proper acceptance criterion must therefore incorporate this uncertainty. Furthermore, the observed trend itself may be incompatible with the model's forcing or parameterization characteristics, meaning that some deviation is expected by construction.

We formalize this idea in the acceptance criterion presented in Section 5, which requires that the difference between modelled and observed trends does not exceed a threshold set by the natural variability of the emulated model.

Figure 3: (a) Temperature and (b) Salinity trend estimates in the 150-600 m layer using different record lengths

3. THE BOX MODEL FRAMEWORK

3.1 Model Design and Philosophy

The box model is designed to represent the large-scale heat and salt content variability of the Mediterranean Sea using a minimal set of prognostic variables and processes. The Mediterranean is divided into 6 well-mixed boxes representing the major sub-basins and depth layers. Each box exchanges heat and salt with its neighbours through parameterized horizontal and vertical transport, and interacts with the atmosphere through surface heat and freshwater fluxes, and with the Atlantic Ocean through the Strait of Gibraltar. In this work we use a modified version of the box model proposed by Llasses et al. (2016, see Figure 4).

The key advantage of this approach is computational efficiency. Once calibrated, the box model can be integrated for centuries in a short time, allowing for large ensembles of sensitivity experiments that would be prohibitively expensive with a full numerical model. At the same time, the model is constrained to be consistent with the numerical model whose it has been calibrated to reproduce.

The box model equations are the following:

Equations temperature

$$dT_{1w} = [FG1(TFG1) + F_{21w}(T_{2w}) - K_{12w}(T_{1w} - T_{2w}) - F_{13w}(T_{13w}) - FS1(T_{1w}) - SHFw] \cdot \frac{dt}{V_{1w}}$$

$$dT_{1e} = [FS1(T_{1w}) - K_{12e}(T_{1e} - T_{2e}) - F_{12e}(T_{12e}) - F_{13}(T_{13e}) - SHFE] \cdot \frac{dt}{V_{1e}}$$

$$dT_{2w} = [F_{13w}(T_{3w}) + k_{12w}(T_{1w} - T_{2w}) + FS2(T_{2e}) - FG2(T_{2w}) - F_{21w}(T_{2w}) - K_{23w}(T_{2w} - T_{3w})] \cdot \frac{dt}{V_{2w}}$$

$$dT_{2e} = [K_{12e}(T_{1e} - T_{2e}) + F_{12e}(T_{12e}) + K_{23e}(T_{2e} - T_{3e}) + F_{13e}(T_{3e}) - FS2(T_{2e})] \cdot \frac{dt}{V_{2e}}$$

$$dT_{3w} = [F_{13w}(T_{13w}) + K_{23w}(T_{2w} - T_{3w}) - F_{13w}(T_{3w})] \cdot \frac{dt}{V_{3w}}$$

$$dT_{3e} = [K_{23e}(T_{2e} - T_{3e}) + F_{13e}(T_{13e}) - F_{13e}(T_{3e})] \cdot \frac{dt}{V_{3e}}$$

Equations salinity

$$dS1w = [FG1(SFG1) + F21w(S2w) - K12w(S1w - S2w) - F13w(S13w) - FS1(S1w)] \cdot \frac{dt}{V1w}$$

$$dS1e = [FS1(S1w) - K12e(S1e - S2e) - F12e(S12e) - F13(S13e)] \cdot \frac{dt}{V1e}$$

$$dS2w = [F13w(S3w) + k12w(S1w - S2w) + FS2(S2e) - FG2(S2w) - F21w(S2w) - K23w(S2w - S3w)] \cdot \frac{dt}{V2w}$$

$$dS2e = [K12e(S1e - S2e) + F12e(S12e) + K23e(S2e - S3e) + F13e(S3e) - FS2(S2e)] \cdot \frac{dt}{V2e}$$

$$dS3w = [F13w(S13w) + K23w(S2w - S2w) - F13w(S3w)] \cdot \frac{dt}{V3w}$$

$$dS3e = [K23e(S2e - S3e) + F13e(S13e) - F13e(S3e)] \cdot \frac{dt}{V3e}$$

Where indices 1,2,3 refer to surface, intermediate and deep layer, “e” and “w” to the eastern and western basins, respectively, F to advective fluxes, K to turbulent fluxes, SHF to surface net heat flux, EPR to surface net water balance and FG the fluxes through the Gibraltar Strait.

Figure 3: Sketch of the three-layer box model used in this study.

3.2 Calibration Against CNRM-RCSM6

We calibrate the box model using the control run of the CNRM-RCSM6 regional climate model (Darmaraki et al., 2019, <https://cnrm.sedoo.fr/cnrm-resm6/>), which provides a multi-decadal simulation without anthropogenic forcing (i.e., no climate change signal) over the period 1980–2100. The control run provides time-evolving surface fluxes, Atlantic boundary conditions, and internal temperature and salinity fields that are used both to force the box model and to determine its optimal exchange coefficients.

The calibration procedure minimizes the misfit between the box model output and the CNRM-RCSM6 control run time series for each box. The resulting exchange coefficients represent the model genome of CNRM-RCSM6, encapsulating its characteristic mixing rates and inter-basin exchange properties (see Table 1 for the model genome).

Validation of the calibrated box model against the CNRM-RCSM6 control run shows excellent agreement for the surface (0–150 m) and intermediate (150–600 m) layers, for both temperature and salinity (Figure 4 and Figure 5). Agreement is somewhat reduced for the deep layer (600 m–bottom), where internal mixing processes are less well captured by the simplified box structure. Nevertheless, the box model successfully reproduces the dominant modes of variability across all layers, confirming its suitability for long-term sensitivity experiments.

Figure 4: Comparison of emulated and target time series of temperature in the 6 box-model compartments (blue: Box-Model, red: CNRM-RCSM6)

Figure 5: Comparison of emulated and target time series of salinity in the 6 box-model compartments (blue: Box-Model, red: CNRM-RCSM6)

Table 1: Initial and optimized values of the different free parameters of the Box Model adjusted to the CNRM-RCSM6 model (the model “genome”)

	Initial values	Optimized values
<i>F13W</i>	$0.31 \cdot 10^5 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$	$5.56 \cdot 10^6 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$
<i>F13E</i>	$0.51 \cdot 10^5 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$	$1.24 \cdot 10^6 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$
<i>K12W</i>	$1 \cdot 10^5 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$	$1.85 \cdot 10^6 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$
<i>K23W</i>	$1 \cdot 10^5 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$	$2.99 \cdot 10^6 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$
<i>K12E</i>	$1 \cdot 10^5 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$	$0.46 \cdot 10^6 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$
<i>K23E</i>	$1 \cdot 10^5 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$	$2.99 \cdot 10^6 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$
<i>DT13W</i>	$3.40 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$	$3.05 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$
<i>DT13E</i>	$3.40 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$	$3.34 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$
<i>DT12E</i>	$2.46 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$	$0.36 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$
<i>DS13W</i>	1.10 psu	0.69 psu

<i>DS13E</i>	0.10 <i>psu</i>	0.76 <i>psu</i>
<i>DS12E</i>	0.20 <i>psu</i>	3.28 <i>psu</i>

4. MULTI-CENTENNIAL EXPERIMENTS AND NATURAL VARIABILITY

4.1 Experimental Design

To characterize the natural variability of Mediterranean temperature and salinity and its influence on trend uncertainty, we force the calibrated CNRM-RCSM6 box model with multi-centennial outputs from the CNRM-ESM2 global model control run (1900–2400). This provides a stationary, multi-centennial realization of the atmospheric and Atlantic boundary forcing free of climate change signal, from which we can estimate the full distribution of internal variability in the CNRM-RCSM6 model. By integrating the box model over this extended period, we generate synthetic temperature and salinity time series for each sub-basin and depth layer that are consistent with the CNRM-RCSM6 genome but encompass a much wider range of natural variability than the original control run (Figure 6).

Figure 6: Multicentennial simulation of the Box-Model using the CNRM-RCSM6 genome and forced with the surface fluxes and Atlantic conditions extracted from the CNRM-ESM2 global simulation. (Left) temperature time series (Right) Salinity time series. Top panels are for the western basin and lower panels for the eastern basin.

4.2 Natural Variability of Trend Estimates

From the multi-centennial box model run, we extract linear trends over sliding windows of 20, 40, and 60 years (consistent with the observational analysis in Section 2). The resulting distributions of trend values quantify the natural variability uncertainty, i.e., the range of trends that could be produced by the emulated CNRM-RCSM6 model purely due to internal variability, without any forced climate change signal or spin-up artifact.

As an example, the results for the 150–600 m salinity layer in the Western and Eastern Mediterranean show that trend uncertainty decreases with increasing window length, as expected (Figure 7). For 60-year windows, the interquartile range of the trend distribution is approximately ± 0.010 psu/decade in the intermediate layers, providing a quantitative bound on the natural variability contribution to observed trends.

5. ACCEPTANCE CRITERIA FOR SPIN-UP ADEQUACY

Based on the above analysis, we propose the following formal acceptance criterion for spin-up adequacy. Let T^{obs} be the observed trend over a reference period of a given length, T^{Mod} be the trend in a given model simulation, and σ_{NatVar} be the standard deviation of the natural variability trend distribution estimated from the multi-centennial box model run. A model simulation is deemed acceptable if:

$$|T^{Obs} - T^{Mod}| < \sqrt{2} \sigma_{NatVar}$$

Or

$$|T^{Obs} - \sqrt{2} \sigma_{NatVar}| < T^{Mod} < T^{Obs} + \sqrt{2} \sigma_{NatVar}$$

The factor $\sqrt{2}$ arises from combining the independent natural variability contributions from the modelled and observed trend estimates in quadrature. This criterion is analogous to a two-sample test for trend compatibility under the null hypothesis that model and observations sample the same underlying variability distribution.

This criterion can be applied separately to each sub-basin (Western, Eastern) and depth layer, and for both temperature and salinity. Table 2 summarizes the observed 60-year trends and the emulated natural variability uncertainty ranges for temperature and salinity across all Mediterranean sub-basin and depth-layer combinations considered in this study. These values provide the quantitative basis for applying the acceptance criterion in future model evaluations.

REPENSAR SI EL CALCUL DELS LIMITS ÉS CORRECTE – Revisar les estimacions de sigma nat. variability

Table 2: Salinity trends (in psu/decade) computed using different record lengths (15, 30 and 60 yrs) for each subbasin and layer. For each record length it is shown the median value from observational records (OT), the box-model based estimate of natural variability (σ_{NatVar}), the lower and the upper limit of acceptable model trends

Salinity Trends (psu/dec)		Estimates using 15 year periods				Estimates using 30 year periods				Estimates using 60 year periods			
Basin	Layer	OT	NV	Lower Limit	Upper limit	OT	NV	Lower Limit	Upper limit	OT	NV	Lower Limit	Upper limit
Western	0-150m	0.04	0.07	-0.05	0.13	0.01	0.03	-0.03	0.05	0.02	0.01	0.00	0.03
	150-600m	0.02	0.03	-0.02	0.05	0.02	0.01	0.00	0.03	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.02
	600m-bottom	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.02	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.02	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.02
Eastern	0-150m	0.01	0.04	-0.05	0.07	0.01	0.02	-0.02	0.04	0.01	0.01	-0.01	0.03
	150-600m	0.00	0.02	-0.03	0.04	0.01	0.01	-0.01	0.02	0.01	0.01	-0.01	0.02
	600m-bottom	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.01

Table 3: Temperature trends (in °C/decade) computed using different record lengths (15, 30 and 60 yrs) for each subbasin and layer. For each record length it is shown the median value from observational records (OT), the box-model based estimate of natural variability (σ_{NatVar}), the lower and the upper limit of acceptable model trends

Temp. Trends (°C/dec)		Estimates using 15 year periods				Estimates using 30 year periods				Estimates using 60 year periods			
Basin	Layer	OT	NV	Lower Limit	Upper limit	OT	NV	Lower Limit	Upper limit	OT	NV	Lower Limit	Upper limit
Western	0-150m	0.14	0.36	-0.37	0.64	0.08	0.20	-0.21	0.37	0.05	0.06	-0.04	0.14
	150-600m	0.04	0.27	-0.34	0.41	0.01	0.18	-0.24	0.26	0.01	0.05	-0.06	0.09
	600m-bottom	0.03	0.14	-0.17	0.22	0.00	0.12	-0.17	0.17	0.00	0.03	-0.04	0.04
Eastern	0-150m	0.12	0.66	-0.81	1.06	0.00	0.29	-0.41	0.41	0.04	0.08	-0.07	0.14
	150-600m	0.00	0.32	-0.45	0.46	-0.05	0.22	-0.36	0.27	-0.02	0.06	-0.10	0.06
	600m-bottom	0.01	0.14	-0.18	0.21	-0.03	0.13	-0.21	0.15	-0.02	0.03	-0.06	0.03

7. DISCUSSION

The box model framework presented here offers several practical advantages for the evaluation of model spin-up. First, its computational cost is negligible compared to full regional climate model integrations, allowing large ensembles and multi-centennial runs that are not feasible with full models. Second, by calibrating the box model to a specific numerical model's genome, we ensure that the emulated natural variability is physically consistent with that model's dynamics, rather than relying on generic climatological estimates.

Third, the framework is modular: the same box model structure can be calibrated to any regional climate model for which a multi-decadal control run is available, enabling systematic inter-model comparisons of spin-up behaviour and natural variability. This makes the approach well-suited for community protocols such as those being developed within the CORDEX framework.

The box model necessarily simplifies the three-dimensional dynamics of the Mediterranean Sea. In particular, the representation of deep-water formation, convective mixing, and mesoscale eddy transport is highly parameterized, leading to reduced fidelity in the deep layer relative to the surface and intermediate layers. The acceptance criterion proposed in Section 5 should therefore be applied with greater caution for deep-water trend evaluations.

Additionally, the calibration is based on a single reference model (CNRM-RCSM6) and a specific set of boundary conditions. The generality of the results to other model configurations and forcing datasets has yet to be established. The next steps outlined below address this limitation.

Finally, the observational estimates of trends and their uncertainties carry their own limitations, including inhomogeneous sampling, instrumental errors, and differences in data assimilation methodologies across products. These observational uncertainties enter the acceptance criterion through the observed trend term and should be propagated explicitly in a full uncertainty analysis.

Several extensions of the current work are planned. First, the calibration and validation of the box model will be repeated for additional regional climate models participating in the CORDEX Mediterranean ensemble, enabling a systematic assessment of genome variability and its consequences for spin-up requirements.

Second, additional global model control runs will be used to force the box model, allowing the characterization of natural variability uncertainty across different background states. Third, sensitivity experiments with different spin-up forcing strategies — including random-year cycling, repeated-decade cycling, and direct initialization from climatology — will be systematically compared to assess their relative efficiency and artifact characteristics.

A particularly promising application is the use of a short-period calibration run to estimate the model genome and the stable initial conditions implied by that genome. If successful, this approach could dramatically reduce the spin-up period required to reach equilibrium by initializing the

model at a state already consistent with its own dynamics, rather than at an arbitrary observational estimate.

8. CONCLUSIONS

This paper has presented a box-model approach to quantify errors in long-term ocean temperature and salinity trend estimates arising from insufficient spin-up in regional ocean models of the Mediterranean Sea. The key findings are as follows:

Observed trends computed over 60-year records from different observational products show significant inter-product spread, and are strongly sensitive to the length of the record considered. This observational uncertainty must be accounted for when using observed trends as constraints for model evaluation.

A simple box model can be calibrated to the large-scale heat and salt content dynamics of the CNRM-RCSM6 regional climate model with high fidelity in the surface and intermediate layers. When forced by multi-centennial output from the CNRM-ESM2 global model, the calibrated box model provides a rich characterization of natural variability.

The natural variability envelope of 60-year trend estimates derived from the box model provides a physically grounded acceptance criterion for spin-up adequacy. A model simulation is acceptable if the difference between its trend and the observed trend does not exceed $\sqrt{2}$ times the natural variability standard deviation.

The box model framework is computationally inexpensive, physically interpretable, and transferable to other regional climate models, making it a valuable tool for community protocols on spin-up evaluation within CORDEX and similar initiatives.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The author thanks F. Sevault (Météo-France) for providing the observational product time series and the CNRM-RCSM6 and CNRM-ESM2 model data. This work was conducted in the framework of the MedCORDEX Protocol Task Team on Model Spin-Up. The CNRM-RCSM6 and CNRM-ESM2 model data were made available through the CNRM team at Météo-France.

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